

JASMIN Overview

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W?

- What is it?
 - Petascale storage and cloud computing for big data challenges in environmental science
 - 13 Petabytes disk
 - 3600 computing cores (HPC, Virtualisation)
 - High-performance network design
 - Private clouds for virtual organisations
- For Whom?
 - Entire NERC community
 - Met Office
 - European agencies
 - Industry partners
- For What?
 - Everything CEDA did before
 - Curation, Facilitation (e.g. BADC, ESGF, ...)
 - Collaborative workspaces
 - Scientific analysis environment

CEDA: Evolution

Data growth

(Credit: Folkes, Churchill)

Light blue = total of all tape at STFC

Green = Large Hadron Collider (LHC) Tier 1 data on tape

Dark blue = data on **disk** in JASMIN

Data growth on JASMIN has been limited by:

Not enough disk (now fixed ...for a while)

Not enough local compute (now fixed ...for a while)

Not enough inbound bandwidth (now fixed ...for a while)

Missing piece

- Urgency to provide better environmental predictions
- Need for higher-resolution models
- HPC to perform the computation
- Huge increase in observational capability/capacity

But...

- Massive storage requirement: observational data transfer, storage, processing
- Massive raw data output from prediction models
- Huge requirement to process raw model output into usable predictions (graphics/post-processing)

Hence JASMIN...

ARCHER supercomputer (EPSRC/NERC)

JASMIN (STFC/Stephen Kill)

JASMIN Phase 1

2012 UK Government capital investment

- JASMIN
 - Climate science, Earth System modelling focus
 - Support UK and European HPC facilities
- CEMS (facility for Climate and Environmental Monitoring from Space)
 - Earth Observation focussed
 - An industry-academic partnership

JASMIN Phase 1: Logical view

JASMIN Phase 1

Configured as a storage and analysis environment

2 types of compute:

- virtual/cloud environment
 - flexibility
- batch compute
 - Performance

Both connect to 5 Pb of fast parallel disk Network

Internal: Gnodal

External:

JANET (UK)

OPNS to key partner institutions

JASMIN

jasmin-login1

SSH login gateway

jasmin-xfer1

Data transfers

firewall

jasmin-sci1

Science/analysis

lotus.jc.rl.ac.uk

Batch processing cluster

CEMS

cems-login1

SSH login gateway

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cems-sci1

Science/analysis

Model for JASMIN 1

Key:

- General-purpose resources
- Project-specific resources
- Data centre resources

JASMIN 1 Results and Lessons Learnt

140-185 jobs in parallel with no I/O issues.

Each colour represents a node, 12 cores / node

Network diagram shows switches saturating but storage still has spare b/w

- JASMIN has
 - proprietary parallel file system (Panasas) with high I/O performance
 - bare-metal compute cluster
 - virtualisation and cloud via VMware vCloud
- Success for batch compute
 - ATSR full-mission reprocessing: **One month's L1B data processing in 12 minutes where on previous system it took 3 days!**
- Virtualisation rather than full cloud
 - Provision hosts for users via helpdesk and virtualisation tools
- Usability and user management
 - Technically difficult for some users
 - Not enough control for other users (root)
 - Help and support too labour intensive
- Summary: service delivery needs to catch up with raw infrastructure power!

JASMIN 1 Success: UPSCALE

- 250 Tb in 1 year from PRACE supercomputing facility in Germany (HERMIT)
- Network transfer to JASMIN
- Analysed by Met Office scientists as soon as available
- Deployment of VMs running custom scientific software, co-located with data
- Outputs migrated to long term archive (BADC)

Image: P-L Vidale & R. Schiemann, NCAS

Mizielinski et al (Geoscientific Model Development, submitted)
“High resolution global climate modelling; the UPSCALE project, a large simulation campaign”

Phase 2/3 expansion

- 2013 NERC Big Data capital investment
 - Wider scope: support projects from new communities, e.g.
 - EOS Cloud
 - Environmental 'omics. Cloud BioLinux platform
 - Geohazards
 - Batch compute of Sentinel-1a SAR for large-scale, hi-res Earth surface deformation measurement

Sentinel-1a (ESA)

	Phase 2 by March 2014	Phase 3 by March 2015
JASMIN hard upgrade	+7 Petabytes disk +6 Petabytes tape +3000 compute cores network enhancement	+o(2) Petabytes disk +o(800) compute cores network enhancement
JASMIN soft upgrade	Virtualisation software Scientific analysis software Cloud management software Dataset construction Documentation	

JASMIN Now

5+7+1=13 PB Disk
Batch Compute
Host Compute

Phase 1 and Phase 2 co-exist
(will be joined as part of Phase 3)

Storage: Panasas

- Used for
 - Archive and Group workspaces
 - Home directories
- Parallel file system (cf Lustre, GPFS, pNFS etc)
 - Single Namespace
 - 140GB/sec benchmarked (95 shelves PAS14)
 - Access via PanFS client/NFS/CIFS
 - POSIX filesystem out of the box.
- Mounted on Physical and Virtual Machines
- 103 shelves PAS11 + 101 shelves PAS14
 - Each shelf connected at 10Gb (20Gb PAS14)
 - 2,244 'Blades' (each with network address!)
 - JASMIN - Largest single realm in the world
- One Management Console
- TCO: *Big Capital, Small Recurrent*
but JASMIN2 £/TB < GPFS/Lustre offerings

Storage: NetApp

- Used for
 - Virtual Machine OS image storage
 - Cloud Data storage (on VMDK's)
 - Lower performance (NFS)
- 900TB. Cluster config of 4x FAS6250's controllers
 - Redundant pair per disc chain
 - SAS Disc chains of 10 shelves x 24 discs
- One Management Console for whole system
- TCO: *Medium Capital,*
 - *Medium Performance, Small Recurrent*
- More complex than Panasas to deploy
 - 1 week install + 1 week configuration for 900TB vs.
 - 3 day physical install and configuration for 7PB

Storage: Elastic tape

- Robot tape already in use for CEDA Archive secondary copy
 - CERN CASTOR system used for LHC Tier1
 - Oracle/StorageTek T10KC
- Requirement
 - Enable JASMIN GWS managers to make best use of (expensive!) high-perf disk
 - Move data to/from group workspace
 - Tools for them to do it themselves
 - Not traditional “backup” system
 - Scales & use cases too diverse

isgtw.org / gridpp

Compute

Model	Processor	Cores	Memory
194 x Viglen HX525T2i	Intel Xeon E5-2650 v2 "Ivy Bridge"	16	128GB
14 x Viglen HX545T4i	Intel Xeon E5-2650 v2 "Ivy Bridge"	16	512GB
6 x Dell R620	Intel Xeon E5-2660 "Sandy Bridge"	16	128GB
8 x Dell R610	Intel Xeon X5690 "Westmere"	12	48GB
3 x Dell R610	Intel Xeon X5675 "Westmere"	12	96GB
1 x Dell R815	AMD Opteron	48	256GB

- 226 bare metal hosts
- 3556 cores
- 2 x 10Gb Ethernet (second interface for MPI traffic)
- Intel / AMD processors available
- 17 large memory hosts
- More than 1.3M jobs over two years
- **Hosts can be easily redeployed as VMware/LOTUS nodes**

Compute: LOTUS

- RHEL + Platform LSF 8
 - LSF 9 Upgrade planned
- Storage
 - CEDA (BADC, NEODC) archives mounted RO
 - Group Workspaces mounted RW
 - /home/users
- Software
 - PGI, Intel compilers
 - Platform MPI
 - JASMIN Analysis Platform
 - /apps for user-requested software
- Job submission
 - From LOTUS head node, *sci VMs or specific project VMs

Networking: key features

- It's big
 - >1000 ports @ 10Gb
 - >26 switches
 - Ability to expand to >1700 ports @ 10Gb
- High performance, low latency
 - Any port to any port is non-blocking: no contention
- Outside-world connections
 - 40GbE via RAL site & firewall
 - 10GbE Science DMZ
 - OPNs (Light Paths) to UKMO, Edinburgh, Leeds (1-2 GbE)
- Separate management network at 10/100/1000bE of >30 switches, 500 ports

Network: internal

- 48 compute servers per rack
 - 5 network cables per server.
 - Red: 100Mb network management console
 - Blue: redundant 1Gbit virtualisation management network
 - Black: 2x10Gb network cables.
 - 96 x 10Gb cables per rack patched to 2 Mellanox switches at bottom of rack. Mellanox provides unique technology to minimise network contention
 - Orange: 12 x 40Gb uplinks per switch
- 23 such 10Gb switches
>1000 x 10G ports
>3 Terabit/sec

Network: internal

- 12 x 40Gb Mellanox switches
 - 1 connection to each bottom-of-rack switches
 - Complete redundant mesh
- RAL site has 40Gb connection to JANET/internet using same 40Gb connections!
- 204 x 40Gb cables provides bandwidth of over 1 Terabyte / sec internal to JASMIN2
- Phase 3 connects JASMIN1 to JASMIN2 via yellow 56Gbit cables

Design challenge: space to expand

Science DMZ

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Management & Monitoring

- Kickstart/Deployment system
- Puppet control of key configs
- Yum repos (100+ Science rpms)
- LDAP Authentication
 - Driven from CEDA user mgmt DB
- Ganglia Web inc power, power, humidty.
 - User accessible
- Network monitoring (Cacti, Observium, sFlow)
 - Overview user accessible via 'Dashboard'
- Nagios alerting (h/w and services)
- Intrusion detection (AIDE)
- Universal syslog (Greylog2)
- Root command logging
- Patch Monitoring (Pakiti)
- Dedicated helpdesks
- Fulltime machine room OPs staff

JASMIN/CEMS Environmental Conditions

JASMIN Analysis Platform

- Software stack enabling scientific analysis on JASMIN.
 - Multi-node infrastructure requires a way to install tools quickly and consistently
 - The community needs a consistent platform wherever it needs to be deployed.
 - Users need help migrating analysis to JASMIN.

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/cedaservices/wiki/JASMIN/AnalysisPlatform>

What JAP Provides

- **Standard Analysis Tools**
 - NetCDF4, HDF5, Grib
 - Operators: NCO, CDO
 - Python Stack
 - Numpy, SciPy, Matplotlib
 - IRIS, cf-python, cdat_lite
 - IPython
 - GDAL, GEOS
 - NCAR Graphics, NCL
 - R, octave
 - ...
- **Parallelisation and Workflow**
 - Python MPI bindings
 - Jug (simple python task scheduling)
 - IPython notebook
 - IPython-parallel
 - JASMIN Community Inter-comparison Suite

Community Intercomparison Suite (CIS)

CIS = Component of JAP

Time-series

Line plots

Scatter plots

Global plots

Curtain plots

Overlay plots

Histograms

Dataset	Format
AERONET	Text
MODIS	HDF
CALIOP	HDF
CloudSAT	HDF
AMSRE	HDF
TRMM	HDF
CCI aerosol & cloud	NetCDF
SEVIRI	NetCDF
Flight campaign data	RAF
Models	NetCDF

CIS – Co-location

```
cis col <variable>:<source file> <sampling file>:colocator=lin -o <new file>  
cis plot <variable>:<new file> <variable>:<sampling file> --type comparativescatter \  
--logx --xlabel 'Observations AOT 675nm' --xmin 1.e-3 --xmax 10 \  
--logy --ylabel 'Model AOT 670nm' --ymin 1.e-3 --ymax 10
```

Model gives global output every 3 hours for a full month

Collocation

Observations are day-time site measurements, every 15 min for a full month

Vision for JASMIN 2 (Applying lessons from JASMIN 1)

- Some key features
 - Nodes are general purpose: boot as bare metal or hypervisors
 - Use cloud tenancy model to make Virtual Organisations
 - Networking: make an isolated network inside JASMIN to give users greater freedom: full IaaS, root access to hosts ...

JASMIN Cloud Architecture

IPython Notebook VM could access cluster through Python API

ssh via public IP

JASMIN Cloud Management Interfaces

CloudBioLinux Desktop

Management via Consortia

Name	Manager
Atmospheric & Polar Science	Grenville Lister
Oceanography & Shelf Seas	
Solid Earth & Mineral Physics	
Genomics	
Ecology & Hydrology	
Earth Observation & Climate Services	Victoria
Geology	
Archive	Sam
Director's cut	Bryan

Further info

- JASMIN
 - <http://www.jasmin.ac.uk>
- Centre for Environmental Data Archival
 - <http://www.ceda.ac.uk>
- JASMIN paper

Lawrence, B.N. , V.L. Bennett, J. Churchill, M. Jukes, P. Kershaw, S. Pascoe, S. Pepler, M. Pritchard, and A. Stephens. **Storing and manipulating environmental big data with JASMIN.** *Proceedings of IEEE Big Data 2013, p68-75, [doi:10.1109/BigData.2013.6691556](https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData.2013.6691556)*

